

Adducts of Copper(II) Carboxylates of Unsaturated Acids with Heterocyclic Nitrogen Bases

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Copper(II) carboxylates of unsaturated acids of formula $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHR})_2$ [where $\text{R}=\text{CH}_3$ and C_6H_5] have been prepared and characterized. They yield two series of adducts of composition $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHR})_2 \cdot \text{L}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHR})_2 \cdot 2\text{L}'$ where $\text{L}=\text{2-methylpyridine (2-MePy)}$, quinoline (Q) and $\text{L}'=\text{pyridine (Py)}$, $\text{3-methylpyridine (3-MePy)}$, isoquinoline (IQ) and $\text{morpholine (Morph)}$. Molar conductance studies show them to be non-electrolytic. Molecular weight studies show that 1 : 1 adducts are dimeric. These have been shown by magnetic and spectral studies to possess a carboxylate bridged structure similar to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate, whilst 1 : 2 adducts are hexa-coordinated polymeric species containing anti-anti bridging carboxylate groups.

STUDIES on copper(II) carboxylates of unsaturated acids are practically non-existent¹⁻⁶ except copper(II) carboxylates of acrylic, vinyl and allyl acetic acids⁷. A distinctive feature of these systems is that the double bond of the unsaturated carboxylate group also coordinates to the copper(II) ion⁷. The present study on the adducts of copper(II) crotonate and cinnamate was undertaken with a view to investigate the effect of the added ligand on the structure and properties of the parent copper(II) carboxylates.

Experimental

Materials used: Basic copper carbonate was purified by repeated washings with hot water to remove soluble impurities. Nitrogen bases (BDH) were fractionally distilled and stored over KOH pellets.

Preparation of carboxylates :

Copper(II) crotonate : Basic copper carbonate (2.86 g ; 12 m mole) was refluxed with crotonic acid (3.44 g ; 40 m mole) in MeOH (100 ml) for 90 minutes. Unreacted copper carbonate was filtered off to give a green filtrate. The filtrate was concentrated and on standing overnight shining green crystals of $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2$ were deposited. These were separated, washed with EtOH and dried in air and finally over P_4O_{10} under vacuum at room temperature.

Copper(II) cinnamate : To a suspension of cinnamic acid (trans- β -phenylacrylic acid) (2.96 g ; 20 m mole) in hot water (50 ml) a 10% solution of NaOH (~3 ml) was added slowly until a clear solution was obtained. The pH of the solution was adjusted at 4.5 ± 0.5 by adding 1 : 1 HCl dropwise. To this clear hot solution, an aqueous solution of copper sulphate pentahydrate (2.74 g ; 11 m mole) dissolved in 8 ml was added with stirring. Bluish coloured $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ was precipitated. It was filtered hot, dried in air and finally over P_4O_{10} under vacuum at 100°.

Preparation of Adducts :

Bis(crotonato)(2-methylpyridine)copper(II) :

Copper(II) crotonate was generated *in situ* by the interaction of basic copper carbonate with crotonic acid in EtOH using same quantities as in the preparation of parent carboxylate. One equivalent of 2-MePy (1.86 g ; 20 m mole) was added to the filtrate. The reaction mixture was refluxed for ten minutes and excess of EtOH was distilled off. The concentrate on cooling deposited fine green crystals of $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2 \cdot 2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N})$. These were separated, washed with acetone, dried in air and finally over P_4O_{10} under vacuum at room temperature.

Bis(cinnamato)(2-methylpyridine)copper(II) :

Copper(II) cinnamate (3.57 g ; 10 m mole) was suspended in $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ (150 ml) and one equivalent of 2-MePy (0.93 g ; 10 m mole) was added. The reaction mixture on refluxing for 15 minutes gave a clear green solution. It was filtered and excess of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ was distilled off. The concentrate on cooling yielded shining green crystals of $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot 2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N})$. These were separated, washed with EtOH and dried in air and finally over P_4O_{10} at room temperature.

All other 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 adducts were prepared using the same method as shown above except that for the 1 : 2 adducts two equivalents of the ligand were employed instead of one.

Copper was determined gravimetrically as $\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2$. C and H analyses were carried out in microanalytical laboratory of this department. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$. Molar conductance studies were carried on 10^{-3}M solutions in MeOH using a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge CL01/02. Magnetic moments were determined by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra were recorded in C_6H_6 and/or MeOH from 12,500—28,500 cm^{-1} on Beckman

TABLE 1—SOME PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COPPER(II) CROTONATE, CINNAMATE AND THEIR ADDUCTS

Compound	Colour	Yield %	Elemental Analysis%					
			Found			Calculated		
			Cu	C	H	Cu	C	H
Parent compounds								
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_4$	Green	55	27.02	40.80	4.50	27.20	41.10	4.28
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$	Blue	64	17.59	60.20	4.20	17.77	60.41	3.91
Mono-amine Adducts								
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_4(2\text{-MePy})_2$	Green	62	19.32	51.10	5.45	19.46	51.45	5.21
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_4(2\text{-MePy})_2$	Green	43	13.88	64.10	5.00	14.10	63.92	4.66
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_4.2\text{Q}$	Green	55	17.28	55.95	5.00	17.53	56.27	4.69
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_4.2\text{Q}$	Green	70	12.86	66.30	4.65	13.06	66.59	4.32
Bis-amine Adducts								
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2.2\text{Pv}$	Dark blue	62	16.03	54.85	5.40	16.23	55.17	5.11
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2.2\text{Py}$	Blue	64	12.12	65.05	4.85	12.32	65.17	4.63
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2(3\text{-MePy})_2$	Blue	50	14.96	56.80	5.95	15.14	57.20	5.72
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2(3\text{-MePy})_2$	Blue	41	11.62	65.95	5.35	11.69	66.23	5.15
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2.2\text{IQ}$	Blue	49	12.84	63.20	4.15	12.93	63.47	4.88
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2.2\text{IQ}$	Purple	56	10.16	69.80	6.10	10.32	70.18	4.55
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2.2\text{Morph}$	Blue	61	15.36	46.80	7.15	15.58	47.08	5.87
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2.2\text{Morph}$	Purple	72	11.85	58.40	6.25	11.95	58.67	6.02

TABLE 2—MOLAR CONDUCTANCE, MOLECULAR WEIGHTS, MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COPPER(II) CROTONATE AND CINNAMATE AND THEIR ADDUCTS

Compound	Molar Conductance $\text{mole}^{-1}\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ in Methanol	Molecular Weight		μ_{eff} B.M.	Magnetic Data Temp. °K	Electronic Spectral Data	
		Found	Calcd.			Band I in cm^{-1}	Band II in cm^{-1}
Parent Carboxylates							
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_4$	14.9	—	467	1.39	289	14,280 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$	—	—	715	1.47	290	14,560 ^c	25,360 ^c
Mono-amine Complexes							
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_4(2\text{-MePy})_2$	25.3	762	653	1.42	288	14,250 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_4(2\text{-MePy})_2$	16.7	989	901	1.49	290	13,910 ^b	26,130 ^{bsh}
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_4.2\text{Q}$	23.4	810	725	1.44	288	13,940 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_4.2\text{Q}$	19.5	994	973	1.50	290	14,120 ^b	26,310 ^{bsh}
						13,920 ^a	—
						14,390 ^b	26,860 ^{bsh}
						14,080 ^a	—
						13,950 ^b	25,970 ^{bsh}
Bis-amine Complexes							
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2.2\text{Py}$	15.7	—	391.5	1.86	287	14,970 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2.2\text{Py}$	16.6	—	515.5	1.87	290	15,190 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2(3\text{-MePy})_2$	29.8	—	419.5	1.82	287	14,980 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2(3\text{-MePy})_2$	23.2	—	543.5	1.86	287	15,280 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2.2\text{IQ}$	19.0	—	491.5	1.89	289	14,930 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2.2\text{IQ}$	21.6	—	615.5	1.88	288	15,770 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3)_2.2\text{Morph}$	22.4	—	407.8	1.90	289	14,640 ^a	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2.2\text{Morph}$	25.5	—	531.8	1.90	288	15,180 ^a	—

a : In methanol ; b : In benzene ; c : Diffuse reflectance spectra.

DK-2UV VIS and Near IR Spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra were recorded in nujol in the region 4,000—650 cm^{-1} on Hilger and Watts H 800 IR Spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Both parent carboxylates and their adducts are coloured solids which are quite stable in air. Copper(II) crotonate and its adducts are soluble in common organic solvents like MeOH, EtOH

and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$. By contrast, copper(II) cinnamate is insoluble but its adducts are soluble in polar solvents. A few adducts are also soluble in non-polar solvents like C_6H_6 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$ and CHCl_3 . Sterically hindered ligands 2-MePy and Q form mono-amine adducts while unhindered ligands Py, 3-MePy, IQ and Morph gave bis-amine adducts irrespective of the amount of ligand used. A bis-amine adduct of hindered ligand 2-MePy was also isolated with copper(II) cinnamate but it was unstable and decomposed to its corresponding

mono-amine adduct on standing. This suggests that *bis*-amine adducts of sterically hindered ligands, if at all formed, are far less stable and decompose to their more stable mono-amine analogues. Elemental analyses (Table 1) suggest that these adducts can be assigned a general formula $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHR})_2 \cdot \text{L}$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHR})_2 \cdot 2\text{L}'$. Molar conductances of their $10^{-3}M$ solutions in MeOH (Table 2) fall in the range, 14.0–29.8 mole⁻¹ ohm⁻¹ cm², which shows that these adducts are non-ionic⁸. Molecular weights, which could be determined for 2-MePy and Q adducts (Table 2) are almost double of the value of their respective monomeric formula weights pointing that the adducts are dimeric species of composition $\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CHR})_4 \cdot 2\text{L}$. *Bis*-amine adducts are either insoluble or insufficiently soluble in C_6H_6 or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$, which precluded their molecular weight determinations.

Magnetic Moments : The magnetic moments of powdered copper(II) crotonate and cinnamate are 1.39 and 1.47 B.M. respectively. Magnetic moments of their mono-amine adducts fall in the range 1.42–1.50 B.M. (Table 2). These figures are less than the spin only moment of 1.73 B.M. for copper(II) ion. This lowering in their magnetic moments points out that the adducts are dinuclear carboxylate bridged species and there is considerable spin-spin interaction between the two copper(II) ions of the dimeric molecule like so many other copper(II) carboxylate bridged adducts^{1,9-10} having syn-syn carboxylate bridged structure similar to copper(II) acetate monohydrate. Copper(II) formate tetrahydrate and copper(II) propionate toluidine show magnetic moments of 1.64 and 1.75 B.M. respectively although these are polymeric in nature but involve anti-anti bridging carboxylate groups.^{11,12} However, polymeric copper(II) formate forms a 1:1 adduct with Py which has dinuclear bridged structure in consonance with its subnormal magnetic moment of 1.15 B.M.¹³ This further lends support to the view that 1:1 adducts are dinuclear syn-syn bridged species. *Bis*-amine adducts have magnetic moments in the range of 1.80–1.90 B.M. generally observed for magnetically dilute copper(II) adducts. This shows that the 1:2 adducts are six coordinated and may be either monomeric having bidentate chelating carboxylate groups or polymeric species containing bridging carboxylate groups of anti-anti stereochemical configuration.

Electronic Spectra : Since copper(II) cinnamate was insoluble, its electronic spectrum was recorded in solid state by diffuse reflectance technique. For purposes of comparison, electronic spectrum of copper(II) crotonate was also recorded in solid state. The electronic spectra of the adducts were recorded in solution. All of the mono-amine adducts and the two uncomplexed parent carboxylates show two bands in their electronic spectra in the regions 13,900–14,500 and 25,300–26,600 cm⁻¹ respectively (Table 2) analogous to

the electronic spectra of dimeric carboxylate bridged adducts of copper(II).^{7,14-16} Band I centred around 14,000 cm⁻¹ suggesting distorted octahedral stereochemistry around copper(II) ion while band II, which appears as a shoulder around 26,000 cm⁻¹ is believed to be a charge transfer band¹⁴. These bands have been assigned to $d_{xz}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions respectively as reported earlier^{7,15}.

Bis-amine adducts show only one band around 15,000 cm⁻¹ pointing octahedral coordination of copper(II)⁷. This band occurs at a higher energy in copper(II) cinnamate *bis*-amine adducts as compared to the corresponding adducts of copper(II) crotonate.

Infrared Spectra : The asymmetric and symmetric COO stretching frequencies for copper(II) crotonate and cinnamate are observed at 1578, 1574 and 1413, 1405 cm⁻¹ and their differences, Δ work up 165 and 169 cm⁻¹ respectively. These observations suggest that these carboxylates are dimeric species containing syn-syn carboxylate bridges analogous to copper(II) carboxylates of unsaturated acids reported previously⁷. Their dimeric nature could have been easily confirmed from molecular weight studies but their insolubility in C_6H_6 or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$ precluded this. A-band in the uncoordinated double bond region also appears in these carboxylates at 1653 and 1640 cm⁻¹. An interesting feature of their infrared spectra is the presence of a band of medium intensity at 1510 and 1495 cm⁻¹ in the region of a coordinated double bond. It implies that these carboxylates may be polymeric species in which dimeric units are linked together through the coordination of double bond of the carboxylate group to the copper(II) ion.

In adducts all the bands originating from the coordinated pyridine and quinoline ligands show a positive shift and this shows that these ligands coordinate through their respective nitrogen atoms¹⁷. In morpholine adducts, NH and COC stretching frequencies show negative and positive shifts respectively indicating that morpholine also coordinates through its nitrogen atom¹⁸.

Asymmetric and symmetric COO stretching frequencies in adducts fall in the regions, 1593–1574 and 1419–1401 cm⁻¹ respectively. On the basis of earlier reports⁷, these values lead to the conclusion that mono-amine adducts are dimeric syn-syn carboxylate bridged species, whilst *bis*-amine adducts may be either monomeric or polymeric species. However, the insoluble nature of the *bis*-amine adducts dissuades us to regard them as monomeric molecules containing chelating carboxylate groups and we conclude that these adducts are polymeric species involving anti-anti bridging carboxylate groups.

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